

Novel Pyrimidine-Based Schiff Base Derivatives: Synthesis, Molecular Docking, and Cytotoxic Evaluation Against Colorectal Cancer Targeting AXL Tyrosine Kinase

R. Priyadarsini, S. Archana*, G. Guhan, J. Hanitha Mathanke

Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, College of Pharmacy, Madras Medical College, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India.

ABSTRACT

The study aimed to design, synthesize, and evaluate a series of novel pyrimidine derivatives as potential anticancer agents targeting colorectal carcinoma, integrating both in silico and in vitro approaches to assess their pharmacological potential. Five pyrimidine derivatives (AS1–AS5) were designed and synthesized through a three-step process involving chalcone formation, cyclization to 4,6-diphenylpyrimidin-2-amine, and Schiff base condensation. Structural characterization was performed using UV–Vis, FTIR, ¹H NMR, and HRMS analyses, with purity confirmed by melting point and TLC. ADME, toxicity, and molecular docking studies against AXL tyrosine kinase (PDB ID: 5U6C) were conducted using SwissADME, Osiris Toxicity Explorer, and AutoDock 4.2, respectively. The cytotoxic potential of the compounds was evaluated on the HCT-116 colorectal cancer cell line using the MTT assay, with 5-fluorouracil as the standard. All synthesized compounds obeyed Lipinski's rule of five and were predicted to be non-toxic. Docking results revealed good binding affinities with AXL kinase, particularly for AS-5. In vitro cytotoxicity testing demonstrated that AS-5 exhibited the highest anticancer activity with an IC₅₀ value of 18.39 μg/mL, followed by AS-4 (37.08 μg/mL) and AS-2 (44.05 μg/mL), showing dose-dependent inhibition of HCT-116 cell proliferation. The combined in silico and in vitro findings confirm that pyrimidine derivatives, especially AS-5, possess strong anticancer potential and favorable pharmacokinetic profiles. These compounds can serve as lead scaffolds for further development of targeted therapies against colorectal carcinoma.

Keywords: Pyrimidine derivatives, Schiff base, AXL tyrosine kinase, colorectal cancer, MTT assay; molecular docking, ADME, cytotoxicity.

INTRODUCTION

Cancer remains one of the most significant global health challenges, characterized by uncontrolled cell proliferation, resistance to apoptosis, and the potential for metastasis[1]. Among the various types, colorectal cancer ranks as one of the leading causes of cancer-related morbidity and mortality worldwide. Despite advances in chemotherapy, radiotherapy, and targeted therapy, the development of drug resistance and adverse side effects continues to limit the effectiveness of current treatments. Therefore, the search for novel, potent, and selective anticancer agents with improved pharmacological profiles remains a crucial focus in contemporary medicinal chemistry[2][3].

Heterocyclic compounds play a pivotal role in drug discovery and development due to their diverse biological activities and structural versatility. Among these, pyrimidine and its derivatives constitute an important class of nitrogen-containing heterocycles that exhibit wide-ranging pharmacological properties such as anticancer, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, and antifungal activities[4]. The pyrimidine ring is a core structural feature in several clinically used drugs, including 5-fluorouracil and pemetrexed, which are well-established anticancer agents. Structural modification of the pyrimidine nucleus has been shown to influence electronic distribution, receptor binding, and overall biological activity, making it an attractive scaffold for designing new therapeutic candidates[5].

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Schiff bases, formed through the condensation of primary amines with aldehydes or ketones, are another versatile class of compounds known for their broad pharmacological potential. The presence of the azomethine ($-C=N-$) linkage contributes to their ability to interact with biomacromolecules such as proteins and enzymes, enhancing their biological activity. Combining the pyrimidine nucleus with Schiff base functionality offers a synergistic approach that may enhance cytotoxic potency through improved receptor interactions and stability within biological systems[6].

In recent years, computational approaches such as molecular docking and ADME (absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion) analysis have become indispensable tools in rational drug design[7]. These techniques help predict pharmacokinetic behavior, drug-likeness, and potential binding affinity to target receptors prior to synthesis, thereby saving time and resources in the drug discovery process. In this context, AXL tyrosine kinase, a member of the TAM (TYRO3–AXL–MER) receptor family, has emerged as a key target implicated in tumor progression, metastasis, and resistance to chemotherapy in colorectal and other cancers. Inhibiting this receptor has shown promising therapeutic potential[8]. The present study focuses on the design, synthesis, and evaluation of five novel pyrimidine-linked Schiff base derivatives (AS1–AS5) as potential anticancer agents. The compounds were synthesized through a multi-step reaction sequence involving chalcone formation, cyclization to form the pyrimidine core, and subsequent Schiff base condensation. Comprehensive spectral characterization was carried out using UV–Visible, FTIR, 1H NMR, and HRMS analyses to confirm structural integrity. *In silico* studies including ADME prediction, toxicity assessment, and molecular docking were performed to evaluate drug-likeness and binding interactions with AXL tyrosine kinase. Furthermore, *in vitro* cytotoxic activity was assessed against the HCT-116 human colorectal carcinoma cell line using the MTT assay, with 5-fluorouracil as the reference standard. This integrated computational and experimental approach aims to identify promising pyrimidine-based molecules with potential anticancer efficacy and favorable pharmacokinetic properties,

contributing to the ongoing pursuit of safer and more effective therapeutic agents for colorectal cancer.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Selection of target

The 3D structure of the AXL receptor tyrosine kinase (PDB ID: 5U6C) was retrieved from the Protein Data Bank for molecular docking studies. The 3D structure of selected target is shown in figure no.1

Fig.no.1: 3D Structure of AXL Tyrosine receptor

Chemistry (Basic Nucleus)

Pyrimidine is a six-membered heteroaromatic compound containing two nitrogen atoms at positions 1 and 3, isomeric with other diazines. It shares structural similarities with pyridine, though the presence of additional nitrogen atoms decreases ring electron density, making electrophilic substitution less favorable and nucleophilic substitution more feasible[4].

Pyrimidine analogues such as *2-aminopyrimidines*, *pyrimidine-2-ones*, and *pyrimidine-2-thiones* exhibit diverse pharmacological activities, including anticancer, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and antiviral effects. Owing to their potent cytotoxic and enzyme-inhibitory potential, pyrimidine-based compounds are particularly promising scaffolds for the design of novel agents targeting colorectal cancer[9]. Structure of Pyrimidine nucleus is shown in figure no.2.

Fig.no.2: Structure & 3d Conformer of Pyrimidine Nucleus

Selection Of ligands for Synthesis

Five pyrimidine-based ligands (AS-01, AS-02, AS-03, AS-04, AS-05) were rationally designed, synthesized, and structurally characterized. Their biological potential was further assessed through *in vitro* evaluation, while *in silico* analyses, including ADMET property prediction and molecular docking studies, were performed to support their pharmacological relevance.

Synthetic scheme

STEP-1 : Synthesis OF α,β -unsaturated ketones (chalcones)

STEP-2 : Synthesis of 4,6-diphenylpyrimidin-2-amine

Chalcone (5 mmol) from step 1 is dissolved in 96% ethanol (20 mL) then guanidine hydrochloride (7.5 mmol, 0.7 g) and solid NaOH (22.5 mol, 0.9 g) were added to this solution. The reaction mixture is heated

under reflux for 10–14 hours. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and water is added. The separated product as a solid is filtered and washed with water to a neutral reaction. Recrystallization from ethanol/toluene mixture (1: 1 by volume) to afford the titled 4-methyl-6-phenylpyrimidin-2-amine[12][13].

STEP -3 :

1) Formation Of Schiff base

The product from step 2 (4,6-diphenylpyrimidin-2-amine) (0.01 M) was dissolved in 20ml ethanol in a round bottom flask. The required aldehyde (0.01 M)

is dissolved in 15ml alcohol, was then added to it. The mixture was refluxed for 5-6 hr. The volume of ethanol was reduced to half by distillation under reduced pressure. The resulting solution was poured on crushed ice. The precipitate which got separated was dried and recrystallized from ethanol[6]

2) PEPTIDE COUPLING REACTION FOR THE COMPOUND AS3 & AS5

Carboxylic acid derivatives (1mmol) and a selected DIPEA (1or2mmol) were dissolved in dry DMF (5mL) and stirred for 15 min. Then, TBTU orT3P was added (1mmol) and mixed for 5min (activation step).

After that time, 4,6-diphenylpyrimidin-2-amine (1mmol) in dry DMF (0.2mL) was dripped to the activated amino acid, and the mixture was stirred for 6 -8 hours. Reaction was quenched with water (10mL), and the white precipitate was separated by filtration and vacuum-dried. Pure compound was isolated by crystallization in acetone.

COMPOUND AS3 STEP-3

COMPOUND AS5 STEP-5

3) CONDENSATION REACTION FOR COMPOUND AS2

4,5-dichloropyridazin-3-ol (0.01 mole) in ethanol is refluxed with required amine derivatives (0.01 mole) for 6 hours. After the completion of reaction, the mixture was taken into a china dish and it was kept on a flame after few minutes, pink cream like solid mass

was appeared after it was cooled for few minutes, a light pink solid mass appeared. This is recrystallized from ethanol to get the desired product. The completion of reaction and the purity of the obtained product was monitored with the help of TLC using hexane/ethyl acetate (1:1) solvent mixture. (M.P – 75°C ; Percentage yield – 78 %)

CHARACTERIZATION

The synthesized compounds were subjected to comprehensive characterization using standard analytical techniques. *Melting points* were measured by the capillary method employing a digital melting point apparatus. Compound purity was verified through thin-layer chromatography (TLC) performed

on silica gel GF254 plates, using hexane–ethyl acetate (7:3) as the mobile phase and visualized under UV illumination. **UV–Visible spectra** were recorded on a *Shimadzu UV-1900i spectrophotometer* within the 200–800 nm range. **FTIR spectra** were obtained by the *KBr pellet method* using an *ABB MB-3000 spectrophotometer* to confirm functional groups. The ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a *Bruker*

AVANCE 400 MHz spectrometer in DMSO with TMS as the internal reference. **High-resolution mass spectra (HRMS)** were obtained using a Waters Xevo G2-XS QToF (ESI positive mode) to confirm molecular mass.

IN VITRO EVALUATION:

In Vitro Anticancer Screening (HCT-116 Cell Line) – MTT Assay

- **Principle**

The MTT assay is based on the conversion of the yellow tetrazolium dye, 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT), into an insoluble purple formazan product by mitochondrial dehydrogenase enzymes of viable cells. The amount of formazan formed is directly proportional to the number of metabolically active cells and inversely related to cytotoxicity. The formazan crystals are solubilized using DMSO, and absorbance is measured spectrophotometrically at 570 nm.

- **Cell Line and Culture Conditions**

The HCT-116 (human colorectal carcinoma) cell line was obtained from NCCS, Pune. Cells were maintained in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10% heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum (FBS), 100 IU/mL penicillin, and 100 µg/mL streptomycin. Cultures were incubated at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO₂ until confluent.

- **Preparation of Test Solutions**

Stock solutions of the synthesized pyrimidine derivatives were prepared in sterile DMSO and serially diluted with complete medium to obtain final concentrations ranging from 6.25 µg/mL to 100 µg/ml.

- **Methodology**

The assay was performed following the procedure of Mosmann (1983). Trypsinized HCT-116 cells were seeded in 96-well plates and allowed to adhere for 48 h. Cells were then treated with different concentrations of the test compounds for 24–48 h. After incubation, the medium was replaced with MTT solution (5 mg/mL in phosphate-buffered saline) and incubated for 4 h at 37 °C. The resulting formazan crystals were dissolved in 100 µL DMSO, and absorbance was recorded at 570 nm using a microplate reader.

- **Calculation of Cell Viability**

$$\% \text{ viability} = \frac{\text{Sample abs}}{\text{Control abs}} \times 100$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Synthesis

The five selected and optimized pyrimidine-based lead compounds were synthesized following standard synthetic procedures and purified by recrystallization. The purity of the products was verified by determining their melting points, while reaction completion was confirmed through thin-layer chromatography (TLC). The synthesized compounds are listed in Table 1.

Table no.1: List of the compounds synthesized

Compound Code	IUPAC Name	Structure
AS1	N-(4,6-diphenylpyrimidin-2-yl)-1-(thiophen-2-yl)methanimine	
AS2	6-chloro-5-[(4,6-diphenylpyrimidin-2-yl)amino]pyrimidin-4-ol	

AS3	<i>N</i> -(4,6-diphenylpyrimidin-2-yl)-5-oxopyrrolidine-2-carboxamide	
AS4	(1 <i>Z</i>)- <i>N</i> -(4,6-diphenylpyrimidin-2-yl)-1-(1,3-thiazol-2-yl)ethan-1-imine	
AS5	4-amino- <i>N</i> -(4,6-diphenylpyrimidin-2-yl)pyrimidine-5-carboxamide	

Insilico studies

For the five designed ligands (AS1–AS5), novelty analysis, ADME property prediction, toxicity assessment, and molecular docking studies were performed. The corresponding results are summarized in Tables 2–5.

A) Novelty Assessment

The novelty of the designed ligands was evaluated using the *PubChem database*[14], and all five

compounds were found to be novel, with no identical structures reported.

B) ADME Properties prediction

ADME properties for the designed ligands were predicted using *SwissADME*[15] and all the five ligands were found to be complied with Lipinski's rule of five. The report I summarized in the table 2

Table no.2: ADME and toxicity profile results

Compound Code	Lipinski Rule	Mutagenic	Tumorigenic	Irritant	Reproductive
AS01	Obey's	NO	NO	NO	NO
AS02	Obey's	NO	NO	NO	NO
AS03	Obey's	NO	NO	NO	NO
AS04	Obey's	NO	NO	NO	NO
AS05	Obey's	NO	NO	NO	NO

C) Bioactivity and Toxicity Prediction

Bioactivity are predicted using *swissADME* and toxicity of the 5 Designed ligands are determined using *Osiris Toxicity Explorer*. All 5 Ligands were

found to be Non-toxic. The report is shown in table 3 and they were further subjected to acute rat toxicity by using **GUSAR software** ; the results are shown in table 4.

Table no.3: Bioactivity and toxicity profile results

Ligand Code	Bioactivity Prediction	Toxicity Evaluation
AS1	<p> ■ Enzyme ■ Cytochrome P450 ■ Family A G protein coupled receptor ■ Ligand-gated ion channel ■ Phosphodiesterase ■ Protease </p>	<p>Enter compound name, SMILES or CAS-no: <chem>c1ccc(cc1)-c2nc(cc3cc(C4=CC=CC=C4)N2)cc3</chem></p> <p> Toxicity Risks mutagenic [?] [?] [?] tumorigenic [?] [?] [?] irritant [?] [?] [?] reproductive effective [?] [?] [?] cLogP [?] [?] [?] Solubility [?] [?] [?] Molweight [?] [?] [?] TPSA [?] [?] [?] Druglikeness [?] [?] [?] Drug-Score [?] [?] [?] </p>
AS2	<p> ■ Transferase ■ Enzyme ■ Traser ■ Protease ■ Kinase ■ Nuclear receptor ■ Oxidoreductase ■ Other cytosolic protein </p>	<p>Enter compound name, SMILES or CAS-no: <chem>Oc1nc2c(nc1c3cc(C4=CC=CC=C4)N2)cc3</chem></p> <p> Toxicity Risks mutagenic [?] [?] [?] tumorigenic [?] [?] [?] irritant [?] [?] [?] reproductive effective [?] [?] [?] cLogP [?] [?] [?] Solubility [?] [?] [?] Molweight [?] [?] [?] TPSA [?] [?] [?] Druglikeness [?] [?] [?] Drug-Score [?] [?] [?] </p>
AS3	<p> ■ Family A G protein-coupled receptor ■ Enzyme ■ Kinase ■ Other cytosolic protein ■ Phosphodiesterase ■ Unclassified protein </p>	<p>Enter compound name, SMILES or CAS-no: <chem>O=C1CC(=O)N1c2nc3cc(C4=CC=CC=C4)N2</chem></p> <p>unknown chirality</p> <p> Toxicity Risks mutagenic [?] [?] [?] tumorigenic [?] [?] [?] irritant [?] [?] [?] reproductive effective [?] [?] [?] cLogP [?] [?] [?] Solubility [?] [?] [?] Molweight [?] [?] [?] TPSA [?] [?] [?] Druglikeness [?] [?] [?] Drug-Score [?] [?] [?] </p>
AS4	<p> ■ Nuclear receptor ■ Transcription factor ■ Enzyme ■ Primary active transporter ■ Protease ■ Family A G protein-coupled receptor ■ Membrane receptor ■ Phosphodiesterase ■ Kinase ■ Ligand-gated ion channel </p>	<p>Enter compound name, SMILES or CAS-no: <chem>Cc1nc2c(nc1c3cc(C4=CC=CC=C4)N2)cc3</chem></p> <p> Toxicity Risks mutagenic [?] [?] [?] tumorigenic [?] [?] [?] irritant [?] [?] [?] reproductive effective [?] [?] [?] cLogP [?] [?] [?] Solubility [?] [?] [?] Molweight [?] [?] [?] TPSA [?] [?] [?] Druglikeness [?] [?] [?] Drug-Score [?] [?] [?] </p>

Table no 4: Acute rat toxicity predicted by GUSAR

AS1	Rat acute toxicity predicted by GUSAR																								
	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0,005 in AD</td> <td>-0,203 in AD</td> <td>0,645 in AD</td> <td>0,310 in AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>345,100 in AD</td> <td>214,200 in AD</td> <td>1508,000 in AD</td> <td>697,700 in AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Acute Rodent Toxicity Classification of Chemicals by OECD Project</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 Classification</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Class 4 in AD</td> <td>Class 4 in AD</td> <td>Class 4 in AD</td> <td>Class 4 in AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>IP - Intraperitoneal route of administration IV - Intravenous route of administration Oral - Oral route of administration SC - Subcutaneous route of administration</p> <p style="color: red;">in AD - compound falls in applicability domain of models out of AD - compound is out of applicability domain of models</p> <p>http://www.pharmaexpert.ru/GUSAR/AcuToxPredict/</p> <p>GUSAR - Prediction of Values for Substances Copyright (C) 2010 A. Zakharov, V. Poroikov & Associates</p>	Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)	Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	0,005 in AD	-0,203 in AD	0,645 in AD	0,310 in AD	Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)	345,100 in AD	214,200 in AD	1508,000 in AD	697,700 in AD	Rat IP LD50 Classification	Rat IV LD50 Classification	Rat Oral LD50 Classification	Rat SC LD50 Classification	Class 4 in AD			
Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)	Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)																						
0,005 in AD	-0,203 in AD	0,645 in AD	0,310 in AD																						
Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)																						
345,100 in AD	214,200 in AD	1508,000 in AD	697,700 in AD																						
Rat IP LD50 Classification	Rat IV LD50 Classification	Rat Oral LD50 Classification	Rat SC LD50 Classification																						
Class 4 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 4 in AD																						
AS2	<p style="text-align: center;">Rat acute toxicity predicted by GUSAR</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0,181 in AD</td> <td>-0,593 in AD</td> <td>0,487 in AD</td> <td>0,489 in AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>570,700 in AD</td> <td>95,830 in AD</td> <td>1153,000 in AD</td> <td>1159,000 in AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Acute Rodent Toxicity Classification of Chemicals by OECD Project</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 Classification</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Class 5 in AD</td> <td>Class 4 in AD</td> <td>Class 4 in AD</td> <td>Class 5 in AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>IP - Intraperitoneal route of administration IV - Intravenous route of administration Oral - Oral route of administration SC - Subcutaneous route of administration</p> <p style="color: red;">in AD - compound falls in applicability domain of models out of AD - compound is out of applicability domain of models</p> <p>http://www.pharmaexpert.ru/GUSAR/AcuToxPredict/</p> <p>GUSAR - Prediction of Values for Substances Copyright (C) 2010 A. Zakharov, V. Poroikov & Associates</p>	Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)	Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	0,181 in AD	-0,593 in AD	0,487 in AD	0,489 in AD	Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)	570,700 in AD	95,830 in AD	1153,000 in AD	1159,000 in AD	Rat IP LD50 Classification	Rat IV LD50 Classification	Rat Oral LD50 Classification	Rat SC LD50 Classification	Class 5 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 5 in AD
Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)	Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)																						
0,181 in AD	-0,593 in AD	0,487 in AD	0,489 in AD																						
Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)																						
570,700 in AD	95,830 in AD	1153,000 in AD	1159,000 in AD																						
Rat IP LD50 Classification	Rat IV LD50 Classification	Rat Oral LD50 Classification	Rat SC LD50 Classification																						
Class 5 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 5 in AD																						

<p>AS3</p>	<p>Rat acute toxicity predicted by GUSAR</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0,343 in AD</td> <td>-0,012 in AD</td> <td>0,823 in AD</td> <td>0,902 in AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>789,500 in AD</td> <td>348,400 in AD</td> <td>2385,000 in AD</td> <td>2860,000 in AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Acute Rodent Toxicity Classification of Chemicals by OECD Project</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 Classification</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Class 5 in AD</td> <td>Class 5 in AD</td> <td>Class 5 in AD</td> <td>Non Toxic in AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>IP - Intraperitoneal route of administration IV - Intravenous route of administration Oral - Oral route of administration SC - Subcutaneous route of administration</p> <p>in AD - compound falls in applicability domain of models out of AD - compound is out of applicability domain of models</p> <p>http://www.pharmaexpert.ru/GUSAR/AcuToxPredict/</p> <p>GUSAR - Prediction of Values for Substances Copyright (C) 2010 A. Zakharov, V. Poroikov & Associates</p>	Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)	Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	0,343 in AD	-0,012 in AD	0,823 in AD	0,902 in AD	Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)	789,500 in AD	348,400 in AD	2385,000 in AD	2860,000 in AD	Rat IP LD50 Classification	Rat IV LD50 Classification	Rat Oral LD50 Classification	Rat SC LD50 Classification	Class 5 in AD	Class 5 in AD	Class 5 in AD	Non Toxic in AD
Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)	Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)																						
0,343 in AD	-0,012 in AD	0,823 in AD	0,902 in AD																						
Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)																						
789,500 in AD	348,400 in AD	2385,000 in AD	2860,000 in AD																						
Rat IP LD50 Classification	Rat IV LD50 Classification	Rat Oral LD50 Classification	Rat SC LD50 Classification																						
Class 5 in AD	Class 5 in AD	Class 5 in AD	Non Toxic in AD																						
<p>AS4</p>	<p>Rat acute toxicity predicted by GUSAR</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0,093 in AD</td> <td>-0,234 in AD</td> <td>0,646 in AD</td> <td>0,437 in AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>441,300 in AD</td> <td>207,700 in AD</td> <td>1578,000 in AD</td> <td>975,100 in AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Acute Rodent Toxicity Classification of Chemicals by OECD Project</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 Classification</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Class 4 in AD</td> <td>Class 4 in AD</td> <td>Class 4 in AD</td> <td>Class 4 in AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>IP - Intraperitoneal route of administration IV - Intravenous route of administration Oral - Oral route of administration SC - Subcutaneous route of administration</p> <p>in AD - compound falls in applicability domain of models out of AD - compound is out of applicability domain of models</p> <p>http://www.pharmaexpert.ru/GUSAR/AcuToxPredict/</p> <p>GUSAR - Prediction of Values for Substances Copyright (C) 2010 A. Zakharov, V. Poroikov & Associates</p>	Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)	Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	0,093 in AD	-0,234 in AD	0,646 in AD	0,437 in AD	Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)	441,300 in AD	207,700 in AD	1578,000 in AD	975,100 in AD	Rat IP LD50 Classification	Rat IV LD50 Classification	Rat Oral LD50 Classification	Rat SC LD50 Classification	Class 4 in AD			
Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)	Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)																						
0,093 in AD	-0,234 in AD	0,646 in AD	0,437 in AD																						
Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)																						
441,300 in AD	207,700 in AD	1578,000 in AD	975,100 in AD																						
Rat IP LD50 Classification	Rat IV LD50 Classification	Rat Oral LD50 Classification	Rat SC LD50 Classification																						
Class 4 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 4 in AD																						
<p>AS5</p>	<p>Rat acute toxicity predicted by GUSAR</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>0,310 in AD</td> <td>-0,111 in AD</td> <td>0,545 in AD</td> <td>0,807 in AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>751,600 in AD</td> <td>285,500 in AD</td> <td>1293,000 in AD</td> <td>2360,000 in AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Acute Rodent Toxicity Classification of Chemicals by OECD Project</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rat IP LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat IV LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat Oral LD50 Classification</th> <th>Rat SC LD50 Classification</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Class 5 in AD</td> <td>Class 4 in AD</td> <td>Class 4 in AD</td> <td>Class 5 in AD</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>IP - Intraperitoneal route of administration IV - Intravenous route of administration Oral - Oral route of administration SC - Subcutaneous route of administration</p> <p>in AD - compound falls in applicability domain of models out of AD - compound is out of applicability domain of models</p> <p>http://www.pharmaexpert.ru/GUSAR/AcuToxPredict/</p> <p>GUSAR - Prediction of Values for Substances Copyright (C) 2010 A. Zakharov, V. Poroikov & Associates</p>	Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)	Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	0,310 in AD	-0,111 in AD	0,545 in AD	0,807 in AD	Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)	751,600 in AD	285,500 in AD	1293,000 in AD	2360,000 in AD	Rat IP LD50 Classification	Rat IV LD50 Classification	Rat Oral LD50 Classification	Rat SC LD50 Classification	Class 5 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 5 in AD
Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)	Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)																						
0,310 in AD	-0,111 in AD	0,545 in AD	0,807 in AD																						
Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)																						
751,600 in AD	285,500 in AD	1293,000 in AD	2360,000 in AD																						
Rat IP LD50 Classification	Rat IV LD50 Classification	Rat Oral LD50 Classification	Rat SC LD50 Classification																						
Class 5 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 5 in AD																						

D) Docking Results

The 5 designed ligands are docked against *AXL Tyrosine Kinase Receptor* (PDB ID-5U6C) using *AutoDock Tools 4.2 (version 1.5.6)*[16], and binding

interactions were analyzed with *BIOVIA discovery studio*. The docking score of ligands are shown below in the table 5 and Visualization of docking Interactions are shown in the Table 6.

Table no.5: Docking score results

Sr.No	Ligand Code	Docking Score In Kcal/Mol.
1	AS01	-8.86
2	AS02	-9.1
3	AS03	-9.11
4	AS04	-8.66
5	AS05	-9.2

Table no.6: Docking interactions of the ligands

Ligand Code	AXL Tyrosine Kinase
AS1	<p>Interactions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> van der Waals Pi-Sigma Pi-Alkyl
AS2	<p>Interactions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> van der Waals Conventional Hydrogen Bond Unfavorable Donor-Donor Pi-Sigma Pi-Sulfur Alkyl Pi-Alkyl
AS3	<p>Interactions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> van der Waals Conventional Hydrogen Bond Pi-Cation Pi-Anion Pi-Sulfur Alkyl Pi-Alkyl
AS4	<p>Interactions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> van der Waals Carbon Hydrogen Bond Sulfur-X Pi-Anion Pi-Sigma Pi-Sulfur Alkyl Pi-Alkyl

CHARACTERIZATION

A) Compound AS-01:

UV Spectrum, λ_{max} (nm): 330.5; **FTIR (KBr, cm^{-1})**; 3100 (Aromatic CH), 1625 (C=N of Pyrimidine ring), 1536 (Aromatic C=C), 689.42 (C-S-C of Thiophene ring); **HRMS (ESI-MS, Positive mode,**

m/z): molecular weight: calculated: 341.4, $[M+H]^+$: 342.10, M^+ : 364.0879 m/z , 100 % abundance = 364.0879 m/z ; **1H NMR Spectrum (DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz, ppm)**: δ , 7.38-7.5 (10H, Aromatic CH), 8.24 (1H, CH of Pyrimidine), 7.7 (3H, CH of Thiophene). Spectrum of the compound AS-01 is shown in Table no.7.

Table no.7: Spectrum of compound AS-01

C) Compound AS-03:

UV Spectrum, λ_{\max} (nm): 250.5; **FTIR** (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3364 (NH of secondary amine), 3053 (Aromatic CH), 1715 (C=O of lactam ring), 1690.39 (C=O of Secondary amide), 1600.6 (C=N of Pyrimidine ring), 1583.9 (Aromatic C=C), 1361 (C-N of Pyrrolidone ring); **HRMS** (ESI-MS, Positive mode, m/z):

molecular weight: calculated: 358.401, $[M+H]^+$: 358.15, M^{+} : 381.1322 m/z , 100% abundance= 381.1322 m/z ; **1H NMR Spectrum** ($DMSO-d_6$, 400MHz, ppm): δ , 7.5-7.7 (10H, Aromatic CH), 7.839 (1H, NH of amide), 8.5-9.5 (1H, CH of pyrimidine), 6.7 (1H, NH of Pyrrolidone), 5.5 (5H, CH of pyrrolidone). Spectrum of the compound AS-03 in shown in Table no.9.

Table no.9: Spectrum of compound AS-03

E) Compound AS-05:

UV Spectrum, λ_{\max} (nm): 256.0; **FTIR (KBr, cm⁻¹):** 3053 (Aromatic CH), 3320 (NH of Aromatic primary amine), 3450 (NH of secondary amide), 1690 (C=O of secondary amide) 1623.7 (C=N of Pyrimidine ring), 1521 (Aromatic C=C); **HRMS (ESI-MS, Positive mode, m/z):** molecular weight: calculated:

368.4, [M+H]⁺: 369.1, M⁺ = 391.1278, 100 % abundance = 391.1278; ¹H NMR Spectrum (DMSO-d₆, 400MHz, ppm): δ , 7.5-7.7 (10H, Aromatic CH), 8.21 (1H, CH of 2-substituted pyrimidine), 8.23 (2H, CH of 4 substituted pyrimidine), 6.75 (2H, NH₂), 10.98 (1H, NH of amide). Spectrum of the compound AS-04 in shown in Table no.11.

Table no.11: Spectrum of compound AS-05

IN VITRO EVALUATION

In Vitro Anticancer Screening (HCT-116 Cell Line) – MTT Assay

Principle

- The *In vitro* determinations of toxic effects of unknown compounds have been performed by counting viable cells after staining with a vital dye. Alternative methods used are measurement of radioisotope incorporation as a measure of DNA synthesis, counting by automated counters and others which rely on dyes and cellular activity.
- The MTT method is simple, accurate and yields reproducible results. The key component is (3-[4, 5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl]-2, 5-diphenyl tetrazolium bromide) or MTT, is a water-soluble tetrazolium salt yielding a yellowish solution when prepared in media or salt solutions lacking phenol red.
- Dissolved MTT is converted to an insoluble purple formazan by cleavage of the tetrazolium ring by mitochondrial dehydrogenase enzymes of viable cells.
- This water insoluble formazan can be solubilized using DMSO. The resulting purple solution is spectrophotometrically measured.
- An increase or decrease in cell number results in a concomitant change in the amount of formazan formed, indicating the degree of cytotoxicity caused by the test material. The results are shown in table 12&13.

FIG NO.3 :Control pictures of HCT-116

FIG NO.4: Differential morphological alterations observed at varying concentrations of AS-4 (A –1 µg/ml; B –2 µg/ml; C –4 µg/ml; D –8 µg/ml; E –16 µg/ml; F –32 µg/ml; G –64 µg/ml; H –128 µg/ml; I –256 µg/ml; J –512µg/ml)

FIG NO.5: Concentration vs % viability graph of the compound AS-4 against the HCT-116

FIG NO.6: Differential morphological alterations observed at varying concentrations of AS-2 (A – 1 µg/ml; B – 2 µg/ml; C – 4 µg/ml; D – 8 µg/ml; E – 16 µg/ml; F – 32 µg/ml; G – 64 µg/ml; H – 128 µg/ml; I – 256 µg/ml; J – 512 µg/ml)

FIG NO.7: Concentration vs % viability graph of the compound AS-2 against the HCT-116

FIG NO.8: Differential morphological alterations observed at varying concentrations of AS-5 (A – 1 µg/ml; B – 2 µg/ml; C – 4 µg/ml; D – 8 µg/ml; E – 16 µg/ml; F – 32 µg/ml; G – 64 µg/ml; H – 128 µg/ml; I – 256 µg/ml; J – 512 µg/ml)

FIG NO.9: Concentration vs % viability graph of the compound AS-5 against the HCT-116

FIG NO : 10 Concentration vs % viability graph of the compound Standard Drug 5-FU against the HCT-116

Table no.12: % VIABILITY OF SYNTHESIZED COMPOUNDS

Concentration	AS-2	AS-4	AS-5	Standard Drug
512	13.222	7.391	4.352	9.351
256	25.912	23.380	9.042	17.551
128	31.924	32.577	15.198	24.879
64	42.821	43.898	23.698	29.776
32	61.277	53.760	42.752	33.458
16	71.355	65.824	55.066	35.834
8	77.416	77.757	64.743	41.675
4	83.245	81.597	77.387	48.995
2	86.722	88.367	83.850	67.420
1	95.789	94.709	92.205	78.640

Table no.13: IC₅₀ values of the synthesized compounds

COMPOUND	IC ₅₀ VALUE (µg/ml)
AS 2	44.048
AS 4	37.088
AS 5	18.399
Standard Drug (5FU)	7.262

CONCLUSION

Five novel pyrimidine derivatives were successfully synthesized and structurally confirmed through multiple spectroscopic techniques. *In silico*

evaluations revealed favorable ADME profiles, absence of predicted toxicity, and strong binding affinities toward AXL tyrosine kinase. *In vitro* cytotoxic studies demonstrated that compounds AS-2, AS-4, and AS-5 exhibited significant anticancer activity against HCT-116 cells, with AS-5 showing the most potent effect (IC₅₀ = 18.39 µg/mL). These findings suggest that pyrimidine-based Schiff base derivatives hold considerable potential as scaffolds for further optimization and development of targeted anticancer agents. Future work will focus on detailed

mechanistic studies and in vivo validation to establish their therapeutic applicability.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We would like to acknowledge the College of Pharmacy, Madras Medical College, for providing the research facilities. We thank the The Gandhigram Rural Institute instrumentation facility for helping us with characterization studies. We would like to thank Bam bio labs for helping us in the in vitro Evaluation.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The author declares there is no conflict of Interest.

REFERENCES

1. Cancer [Internet]. [cited 2025 Mar 21]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cancer>
2. Menon G, Cagir B. Colon Cancer. In: StatPearls [internet]. Treasure Island (FL) StatPearls Publishing, 2025 [cited 2025 Mar 22]. Available from <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK470380/>
3. Kumar A, Gautam V, Sandhu A, Rawat K, Sharma A, Saha L. Current and emerging therapeutic approaches for colorectal cancer: A comprehensive review. *World J Gastrointest Surg.* 2023 Apr 27;15(4):495–519.
4. Haroon ur Rashid, Research developments in the syntheses, anti inflammatory activities and structure–activity relationships of pyrimidines 2021 The Author(s). Published by the Royal Society of Chemistry DOI: 10.1039/d0ra10657g
5. Xu D, Sun D, Wang W, Peng X, Zhan Z, Ji Y, Shen Y, Geng M, Ai J, Duan W. Discovery of pyrrolo[2,3-d]pyrimidine derivatives as potent Axl inhibitors: Design, synthesis and biological evaluation. *Eur J Med Chem.* 2021 Aug 5;220:113497. doi: 10.1016/j.ejmech.2021.113497. Epub 2021 Apr 25. PMID: 33957388.
6. N. D. Thanh and N. T. T. Mai, *Carbohydrate Research*, 2009, 344, 2399-2405,
7. Prieto-Martinez FD, Lopez-Lopez E, Juarez-Mercado KE, Medina-Franco JL. Computational drug design methods-current and future perspectives. In *silico drug design Academic press.* 2019;19-44
8. Targeting AXL in colorectal cancer: a review of the current state of research (*Cancers*, 2022, 14(11), 2511. DOI: 10.3390/cancers14112511)
9. Inoue S, Yamane Y, Tsukamoto S, Murai N, Azuma H, Nagao S, Nishibata K, Fukushima S, Ichikawa K, Nakagawa T, Hata Sugi N, Ito D, Kato Y, Goto A, Kakiuchi D, Ueno T, Matsui J, Matsushima T. Discovery of 5,6,7,8-tetrahydropyrido[3,4-d]pyrimidine derivatives as novel selective Axl inhibitors. *Bioorg Med Chem Lett.* 2021 Sep 15;48:128247. doi: 10.1016/j.bmcl.2021.128247. Epub 2021 Jul 13. PMID: 34271070.
10. T. Narender and K. Papi Reddy, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 2007, 48, 3177-3180,
11. K. Krohn, K. Steingröver and M. Srinivasa Rao, *Phytochemistry*, 2002, 61, 931-936,
12. O. Nerya, R. Masa, S. Khatib, S. Tamir and J. Vaya, *Phytochemistry*, 2004, 65, 1389-1395,
13. J.-H. Chong, C.-F. Hung, S.-C. Yang, J.-P. Wang, S.-J. Won and C.-N. Lin, *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry*, 2008, 16. 7270-7276.
14. Pubchem- <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>
15. SwissADME-<http://www.swissadme.ch/>
16. Docking tool- <https://autodock.scripps.edu/>

HOW TO CITE: R. Priyadarsini, S. Archana, G. Guhan, J. Hanitha Mathanke, Novel Pyrimidine-Based Schiff Base Derivatives: Synthesis, Molecular Docking, and Cytotoxic Evaluation Against Colorectal Cancer Targeting AXL Tyrosine Kinase, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, 1 (10), 827-846. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17493188>

